

Chith: Untitled Improvisation

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ABSTRACT

This untitled improvisation shows new collaborative affordances in the live coding environment Gibber. The duo Chith features one performer programming electronic music while the other programs generative visuals. Their text editors are displayed in a single window, and statistical information is provided to the visual performer to assist in making decisions about mapping instrument outputs to visual elements. A browser-based “spectator” view is also provided, enabling remote viewing of the performance via synchronized streaming of code and executed commands; this removes the need to stream video of the performance as well as any associated video compression artifacts that might occur.

1. DESCRIPTION

This improvisation will be performed in Gibber by the live-coding duo Chith, consisting of Charlie Roberts live coding music and Gillian Smith live coding visuals. Gibber has been refactored with new collaborative features [1] that will be heavily featured in this performance, including new mapping functions and GUI elements which simplify the creation of audio-reactive visuals.

The performance will be rendered remotely using a new “spectator” view added to Gibber, where audience members can open a link in their browser and watch the performance rendered directly inside of Gibber. This avoids the need to stream video and the corresponding visual compression artifacts; Chith often uses lines and borders that are a single pixel in width in their generative visuals that don’t compress well when streaming. An example of these visuals can be seen in Figure 1.

2. TECHNICAL NEEDS

Both performers will be participating in the conference remotely. We will need a technician to open a provided link on a computer connected to the live venue’s projector and sound reinforcement; this link will launch the performance in the previously mentioned spectator mode.

Figure 1: Screenshot from an online performance by Chith

3. REFERENCES

- [1] C. Roberts, I. Hattwick, E. Sheffield, and G. Smith. Rethinking networked collaboration in the live coding environment Gibber. In *Proceedings of the 2022 New Interfaces for Musical Expression Conference*, 2022.

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